

Implementation of EC-Earth 10km global coupled demonstrator and performance analysis

Deliverable D2.11

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 675191

About this document

Work package in charge: WP2 Scalability

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 27 February 2019

Dissemination level: the general public (PU)

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

Recent studies have established that the typical spatial resolutions used for the atmospheric and oceanic components included in the CMIP5 coordinated exercise (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, phase 5), i.e around 100km-150km globally, are a limiting factor to correctly reproduce climate mean state and variability, where processes such as eddies, clouds, orography effects, small scale hydrology etc. are not represented correctly. The latest generation of models, under development or just starting to be used, have grid spacing in the 20-50 km range, and there is evidence that a number of important climate processes is better represented at this resolution (Prodhomme et al, 2016) (e.g. aqua planet, ENSO, satellite validation, blocking, tropical storm numbers, etc.). However, a higher resolution is already needed as very high-resolution global models are expected to improve our predictions and understanding of the effect of global warming on high impact weather events on seasonal, decadal and century timescales (Zhang et al, 2015). For this reason, BSC is developing a coupled version of the EC-Earth 3.2 climate model at a ground-breaking resolution of about 10 km (called T1279-ORCA12).

In the atmosphere, the horizontal domain is based on a spectral truncation of the atmospheric model (IFS) at T1279 (approx. 10 km globally, i.e. the highest resolution we can use with the standard IFS - higher resolutions would require e.g. nonhydrostatic parameterizations) together with 91 vertical levels. The ocean component (NEMO) is run on the so-called ORCA12 tripolar (cartesian) grid at a horizontal resolution of about 1/12° (approximately 6 to 9 km), with 75 vertical levels, whose thickness increases from 1m below surface up to 200m in the deep ocean.

In this deliverable, we will present the work done to develop this configuration during the whole project as well an analysis of the performance of T1279-ORCA12 on the MareNostrum 4 Supercomputer.

2. Conclusion & Results

At the time of delivering this deliverable T1279-ORCA12 is:

- Developed and shared among EC-Earth consortium partners
- Tested and deployed in MareNostrum 3 and MareNostrum 4 high-performance computers
- Used in production for other H2020 projects such as PRIMAVERA
- Used to investigate the scalability of this ultra-high resolution configuration, enabling to push computational challenges of the current HPC generation machines

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
Improve the efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulation on high-performance computing platforms	Yes
Support the end-to-end workflow of global Earth system modelling for weather	Yes

and climate simulation in high performance computing environments	
The European weather and climate science community will drive the governance structure that defines the services to be provided by ESIWACE	No
Foster the interaction between industry and the weather and climate community on the exploitation of high-end computing systems, application codes and services.	Yes
Increase competitiveness and growth of the European HPC industry	No

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Provide services to the user community that will impact beyond the lifetime of the project.	Yes
Improve scalability and shorten the time-to-solution for climate and operational weather forecasts at increased resolution and complexity to be run on future extreme-scale HPC systems.	Yes
Foster usability of the available tools, software, computing and data handling infrastructures.	Yes
Pursue exploitability of climate and weather model results.	Yes
Establish governance of common software management to avoid unnecessary and redundant development and to deliver the best available solutions to the user community.	Yes
Provide open access to research results and open source software at international level.	Yes
Exploit synergies with other relevant activities and projects and also with the global weather and climate community	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Developments of T1279-ORCA12

At the beginning of the project, EC-Earth 3.2 model was provided with two coupled configurations: T255-ORCA1 and T511-ORCA025. Both configurations were developed by the EC-Earth consortium and shared with the community.

BSC started a branch from the EC-Earth 3.2 PRIMAVERA project branch to develop the T1279-ORCA12 configuration. All developments can be tracked in BSC and EC-Earth development platforms:

- EC-Earth development portal: https://dev.ec-earth.org/projects/ecearth3/repository/changes/ecearth3/branches/development/2018/r5206-bsc_primavera_production_T1279-ORCA12
- BSC Earth Gitlab: <https://earth.bsc.es/gitlab/es/auto-ecearth3/issues/489>

Both platforms are not public but the access can be requested to the authors of this deliverable if more details are needed.

There are three main development topics when a new configuration is created:

- Developing the new source code and run scripts for the new configuration. This is done by specifying the T1279-ORCA12 tag in the development branch, to indicate all the special actions taken for this setup. All the code has been versioned and shared with other partners within the EC-Earth development portal.
- Creating all the needed files to start the simulation. This includes initialisation fields and namelists. The main issue, in this case, has been to create proper weight files for the OASIS coupler. To exchange information between components using different spatial grids, this information is required to do all the interpolations and transformations needed from the source to the destination grid. OASIS itself has an executable to create weight files to couple fields from different grids and when we created such a big configuration we realized the algorithm was not optimised to perform computations on these grid sizes. It took more than a week to successfully compute the weights. The OASIS development team was contacted to point out this issue and a new and optimised version of the routine was released by the OASIS team in the summer of 2018.
- Adapting the production workflow manager developed at BSC ([Autosubmit](#)) to this new configuration. The changes were mainly devoted to optimise the data flow by making use of dedicated data transfer nodes available in MareNostrum 4. As the operation in these nodes is based on non-blocking commands which transparently submit data transfer jobs, we had to improve the workflow code to be aware of these underlying jobs not being launched by Autosubmit itself.

At the time of the ESIWACE project, BSC had two different supercomputers in operation. A first version of the configuration was released when BSC was operating [MareNostrum 3](#). This machine allowed the developers to validate the configuration but not to perform a run with the desired number of cores.

In July 2017, [MareNostrum 4](#) was put into operation. This was a brand-new machine that logically required deployment of all the library dependencies and model components of EC-Earth from scratch (main difference with the former machine were Skylake cores with AVX-512 instructions and Intel OPA network). This situation stopped the ongoing work. The installation of all of these dependencies was done in collaboration with the Operations department of the BSC. However, we had to do different tests to determine which the most robust and efficient libraries and compilation options were, in order to make recommendations to the system administrators of this department. For example, there were issues with netCDF compiled with PNetCDF support, so a version linked without this feature had to be requested (XIOS does not require this feature).

At that point, we were experiencing all the consequences of being early users of new hardware, present in very few HPCs around the world. We had to face a non-negligible number of issues, mainly related to the network layer, which involved many tests to check the efficiency and robustness of the solutions proposed by Operations, mainly configuring several parameters to achieve more stable executions.

Working with the new Omnipath (OPA) network was a challenge at the time of coming up with a stable and reliable configuration. At several stages, we have experienced a different kind of communication

issues, from model crashes to random stops that hampered our operation. In collaboration with the support team of Operations, we tried several networking environment variables to work on network internals, sometimes to change the communication fabric at runtime, other times to use a different version of the PSM2 library (Performance Scaled Messaging by Intel) or change its configuration. The effort needed to solve all these issues led to increasing our communication with the development team of XIOS (the IO server which experienced most of the communication problems).

4.2 Performance analysis

All runs reported in this section were performed in Mare Nostrum 4. See below a summary of the general-purpose cluster system:

- Peak Performance of 11.15 Petaflops
- 384.75 TB of main memory
- 3,456 nodes:
 - 2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 24C at 2.1 GHz
 - 216 nodes with 12x32 GB DDR4-2667 DIMMS (8GB/core)
 - 3240 nodes with 12x8 GB DDR4-2667 DIMMS (2GB/core)
- Interconnection networks:
 - 100Gb Intel Omni-Path Full-Fat Tree
 - 10Gb Ethernet
- Operating System: SUSE Linux Enterprise Server 12 SP2

With EC-Earth being a coupled model, strong scalability tests became a two-dimensional problem, in which for every increment in the amount of resources, the balance between the two major components (IFS & NEMO) had to be achieved.

To find the more balanced configurations for every given amount of resources, two different but complementary approaches were followed. The first (and more costly) one, tries to find the optimal distribution by assigning the same number of processors to IFS & NEMO first, and then moving resources from one model to the other alternately, identifying the intervals in which the model performance increases, by using a variation of the half-interval search algorithm. The second, much cheaper, one starts from one separate scalability test for each one of the components that then was used to determine the best configuration. In our case, the first method could be used to validate the conclusions taken from the second one.

Figure 1: Strong scaling of EC-Earth 3.2 in Mare Nostrum 4 using a T1279-ORCA12 configuration (75 vertical levels, 360 s. timestep) with production output data. The throughput is shown in SYPD.

Figure 1 shows the scalability of EC-Earth for different numbers of processes for the two main components (IFS and NEMO), using the T1279-ORCA12 configuration. The results are evaluated in Simulation Year(s) Per Day (SYPD), a very popular metric in Earth System Modelling. The actual scalability is compared with the ideal scalability (Ideal, in red colour) starting from the smallest case, as well as with the ideal scalability based on the 2,592-core case (Ideal II, in yellow colour) discarding the 1,632-core case for this being particularly inefficient.

Analysing the scalability plot from **Figure 1**, we can see the model does not scale well when increasing the number of cores. This issue can be further investigated collecting traces with hardware counters from a real run. At BSC, we use the combination of EXTRAE as library to extract information of parallel runs and PARAVR as visualisation tool. To find the best number of processes for each component (from a time or energy to solution point of view), an accepted method is to set up the number of processes of each component to achieve a similar SYPD, doing a scalability test of each component independently. The LUCIA tool, integrated into OASIS3-MCT, can be used to explore the load balance of your MPMD Earth System Model in this direction. However, Earth system components usually do not have regular time steps and they include some operations only from time to time (output process, radiation, sea ice calculations...). LUCIA provides total time execution per component, which means that using it to achieve the load balance of your application could result in a setup which does not minimise the idle or waiting time produced when the coupling process is done. Depending on the coupling frequency (the worst case would be a coupling per time step), the load imbalance produced could be significant (up to 15% for the cases presented in Acosta et al. 2016). This means that LUCIA metrics or any other metrics which use total or average execution time are not enough for climate models with irregular coupling time steps of one or more components and other kinds of analysis tools or metrics are needed to study this process (this feature will be developed in the framework of IS-ENES3 project).

Trace details

- Traces extracted using EXTRAE and PARAVER (both tools available from <https://tools.bsc.es/>)
- Time Simulated: 1 Day (24 timesteps)
- Total processes (minimum needed): 1344
- Nemo processes: 720; IFS processes: 432; XIOS processes: 191; runoffmapper: 1
- Coupling frequency: every 2 timesteps
- EC-Earth standard output: Daily

Figure 2: Trace of 24h T1279-ORCA12 execution representing the average MPI call duration

Figure 3: Trace of 24h T1279-ORCA12 execution representing the burst efficiency (blue is better)

191 processes were dedicated to the XIOS server. This is due to high memory consumption of the I/O library. Nodes are fully assigned to XIOS. No tests with different affinity configurations (i.e. mixing cores in a same node) have been performed in this exercise.

The **Figure 2** shows the average MPI call duration (where blue and orange are longest MPI calls and green shorter ones) for a complete one-day simulation along the x axis. The y axis represents the MPI processes; in this case, and following the order, 720 for NEMO, 432 for IFS, 191 for XIOS and finally only 1 for runoff-mapper. There is output (using the output configuration by default set up by EC-Earth) only at the end of the simulation (daily output, orange colour at the end of NEMO and IFS simulation, right orange zones). Additionally, the **Figure 3** shows Burst Efficiency (regions of the code where computational bursts are longer and not interrupted). In this case the efficiency is going from 91% to 52%, and we can see that the worst efficiency, corresponding to yellow colours, occurs in both IFS and NEMO, showing also some load imbalance among processes.

Analysing the traces, we can evaluate how significant and expensive the cost of the IFS output process is, an operation done at the end of the IFS time step (see **Figure 4**, orange region at the end of IFS processes). This cost depends on the output frequency set by the user (though here it is set every 24 hours to reduce the workload of the study, a typical configuration could be every 3 hours). The way that this is typically done is that a master process gathers the data from all MPI sub-domains and prints the complete outputs at a regular frequency of three hours while the rest of processes is just waiting for this to be completed. Considering the volume of data being produced, this sequential process carries a large cost, which increases the final execution time of IFS by 30% when outputs are required. This way of managing outputs is clearly suboptimal when increasing the resolution and allows us to start a promising development to integrate IFS with XIOS I/O library to overcome this bottleneck in the future version of the EC-Earth model. The current EC-Earth version is running ifs36r4 which has been released by ECMWF without I/O server and performs all the I/O sequentially by a master process.

Figure 4: Trace of 24h T1279-ORCA12 execution representing the average MPI call duration with a zoom to catch more details in each time step.

4.3 Outputs from T1279-ORCA12

Different visual material has been produced to disseminate results from this configuration. Below some 2D plots are shown as an example. Some videos are available on YouTube:

Surface current speed in ORCA12 coupled to IFS (EC-Earth 3.2):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pl5QdYRP8qE>

Wind speed at 10m in IFS T1279 coupled to ORCA12 (EC-Earth 3.2):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZwDwy-uGCHM&t=2s>

Figure 5: Left, Global Sea Surface Temperature of the ocean component NEMO. Right, Global Speed Wind at 10m of atmosphere component IFS.

Figure 6: Left, regional crop Sea Surface Temperature of the ocean component NEMO. Right, regional crop Temperature at 2m of the atmosphere component IFS.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

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6. Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU).

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

All the work done to produce this configuration has been shared through the EC-Earth consortium and is ready to be used by all the partners. The deliverable will be provided online in Zenodo.

7. The delivery is delayed: Yes No

8. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

As discussed in 4.2, the main issues were related to MareNostrum 4 and problems detected when running this configuration on a high number of cores. These problems, although blocked us during some months, led us to learn in deep debugging tools as ARM Allinea Studio (in collaboration with WP3 Usability, a hands-on with ARM developers has been held at BSC in May 2018).

9. Sustainability

9.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

BSC computational Earth scientists had learned a lot during the whole process to build this configuration. Overcoming complex technical issues led us to better understand the model and the interactions with current HPC clusters. In addition, the I/O bottleneck in IFS led us to start a new development to couple IFS with XIOS to allow asynchronous I/O and manage all EC-Earth output using

the same I/O library. It led also to release an improved version of Autosubmit workflow manager and OASIS coupler.

The major negative lesson is to avoid changing the development platform during the project (although this situation was not depending on us) and dealing with traces containing this huge amount of information. In order to generate the pictures of this deliverable, we needed to manually pre-process traces to be able to extract useful information.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

There have been many interactions with WP3 regarding the use of debugging tools but also regarding workflow manager tools as Autosubmit. The configuration T1279-ORCA12 has been used in other H2020 projects such as PRIMAVERA and will participate in HighRESMIP exercise within CMIP6. All the performance analysis has been shared with BSC Performance Tools group which is leading the POP CoE. Finally, all the results produced will be distributed and made publicly available using the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) BSC data node.

10. Full track of dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Zenodo record / link to website	Estimated number of persons reached
Others (poster)	“Arsouze T. Running the EC-Earth model at ultra-high resolution, technical and scientific challenges”	EC-Earth meeting, Lisbon (PT), 23 October 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	50
Participation to a conference	Talk: “Serradell, K. EC-Earth, a coupled Climate Model for extreme Event Prediction.”	ISC2018, Frankfurt (DE), 26 June 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	100
Participation to a workshop	Talk: “Neumann, P. - The ESIWACE Demonstrators: Scalability, Performance Prediction, Evaluation.”	5th ENES HPC Workshop, Lecce (IT) 17-18 May 2018	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	60
Participation to a workshop	Talk: “Castrillo, M. Increasing EC-Earth productivity & usability.”	EC-Earth meeting, Reading (UK), 30 January	Scientific Community (higher education,	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	50

		2018	Research)		
Participation to a conference	Talk: "Bilbao, R. EC-Earth ORCA12-T1279 Resolution"	PRIMAVERA 3rd General Assembly, Bologna (IT), 21-23 November 2017	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	60
Participation to a workshop	Talk: "Brodeau, L. EC-Earth ORCA12-T1279."	EC-Earth meeting, Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki (FI), 30 May 2017	Scientific Community (higher education, Research)	https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace	50